

SCREENING AND PREVENTION OF DELIRIUM IN THE INTENSIVE CARE UNIT

Babita Reesaul DNP RN CCRN-CMC, Joy Goebel PhD RN FPCN, Margaret Brady PhD RN CPNP-PC

Background

- Delirium is an acute brain failure
- Incidence in ICU between 15%-89%
- Underrecognized in >65% of ICU patients
- Cost \$164 billion in the United States
- >Mortality, ventilation days, and restraints

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this evidenced based DNP project was to implement and evaluate a nurse-led non-pharmacological delirium prevention bundle in a 32-bed ICU community hospital

Methods

- Setting: 32 bed ICU
- Data Collection: 12 weeks
- Outcome measures:
 - delirium incidence
 - ICU LOS
 - ICU mortality
 - ventilation days
 - restraint usage
 - perceptions of DPB barriers

Supporting Framework

Nurse-Led Non-Pharmacological Delirium Prevention Bundle

- Re-orientation
- Early Mobility
- Sleep Promotion

Results

Delirium Incidence

Outcomes

Secondary Outcomes	Pre DBP (n=61)	Post DBP implementation (n=61)
Delirium Incidence	22 (36%)	10 (16%)
DPB Documentation	61 (100%)	61 (100%)
Restraints	6 (9.8%)	5 (8.2%)
Ventilation days	3.4 (± 2.351)	3.54 (± 2.750)
ICU LOS	4.00 (3-5.5)	4.00 (3-6.5)
ICU Mortality	8 (13.11%)	4 (6.55%)

ICU Mortality & Restraints

Barriers

- Time Consuming
- Lack of Education
- Workload
- Lack of Confidence

Implications for Practice

- Prevention key to delirium ↓
- Cost saving >\$20,000/month
- Standardized screening: CAM-ICU
- Education reduces delirium incidence
- Barriers: resources and self-confidence

Limitations

- Short time frame
- Self report in the nurse survey
- Challenges with competing priorities
- Rosenthal effect (manager implemented project)

Conclusion

- DPB feasible and effective
- Nurses are key to delirium prevention
- Education → Competency and self-confidence
- ↓ Barriers → improved screening, compliance DPB
- Sustainability: EHR and monitoring of outcomes

References

